

The Options Market under a diffusion jump process and a strategy of hedging under a fractional Market

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Abstract

Options have the power to cover a large part of risk without being caught in a crisis of liquidity due to the fact one can get rid of their Option easily, the continuity of the Stock price is a chimera, indeed Stock prices sometimes change with jumps, we did price our Option under such a consideration, afterward we seek shelter in econometrics, as a fact we had changed the trend that raises attention for arbitrage opportunities and their importance for considering how likely the market might show inefficiencies.

We build a theoretical correlation between Vanilla Options and the Stock Market, afterward we investigate when this strategy is arbitrage free.

JEL Classification. D11, G13.

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1 Introduction

The literature of pricing Options gets a larger debt from Stochastic functions and temporary analysis, this article proposes a functional model in continuous time containing a jump diffusion process, however to get this model in accordance with the volatility model which is a discret-time model (FIGARCHS, LONG MEMORY), we would discretize our model afterward, this short article is innovating in term of theory, we did not include an empirical study so far as the main subject of our treatie is a logical algorithm getting Options notably a market that affects the Stock Market positively, which means a theoretical correlation between both Options and Stocks, we baptize this method the

Option multiplier as every time the Option is bought another Stock is getting rough stealing from the risk premium value to change its price afterward.

The assumption we made in the beginning is the fact the Option return exceeds generally the Stock return which is logical as Options are riskier than Stock shares. We realize afterward that our method has some originality and power into defining the Option multiplier as a great method that serves for stabilizing the Stock market, we don't need an empirical study so far as the main assumption of our method is supposing the existence of a kind of investors that would define the behavior of the Stock Market due to their purchasing power.

David S. Bates (1998) has investigated on the equilibrium that allows jumps to occur in a time of a depression, the same author had explained two Option pricing models (2000): Stochastic volatility and jumps, he finds that the Stochastic volatility-jump process models is more convenient to price Options fairly.

Our hypothesis that the Option return exceeds the Stock return comes along with Shumway, Tyler and Coval, Joshua D., Expected Option Returns (June 2000) who study the Options risk of S&P carefully along others phenomena.

2 Model

We suppose the following model for the spot price

$$dS_t = (a - S_t)dt + \sigma_t S_t dW_t + Y_t S_t dN_t$$

Where Y is the intensity of the jump and N is a standard poisson process with intensity λ , σ is the volatility that we would assume to be fractional for the next page.

We would price Vanilla options and Asian options using a numerical method for the coming section, as for now let's write our model for volatility.

The Figarch model is specified as mean reverting equation using the following formula as a starting point:

$$\Phi(L)(1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Psi(L)g(z_{t-1})$$

Where ω is the mean variance and $\Phi(L)$ and $\Psi(L)$ are polynomials in the lag operator, $\Phi(L) = (1 - \Phi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Phi_p L)$ and $\Psi(L) = (1 - \Psi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Psi_p L)$ and $(1 - L)^d$ is the fractional difference operator defined by its binomial expansion:

$$(1 - L)^d = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(i-d)}{\Gamma(-d)\Gamma(i+1)} L^i$$

The function g above is allowed to include the effect past returns has on the current volatility and has the following form:

$$g(z_t) = \theta z_t + \gamma(|z_t| - E|z_t|)$$

where $z_t = \frac{\epsilon_t}{\sigma_t}$ is the normalized innovation

we take into consideration the character volatility always shows as a mean reverting function tending to converge to a constant value and we should define it again as the following:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega)$$

It is then convenient to write the FIGARCH(1,d,1) model as:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Phi_1 h_{t-1} + g(z_{t-1}) + \Psi_1 g(z_{t-2})$$

3 Pricing of Vanilla options and Asian options using a jump process

The price of a Vanilla options with strike K is the following

$$C_t = \exp(-r(T - t))E[(S_T - K)^+/\mathcal{F}_t] \quad (1)$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} & E[S_T \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= E[S_0 + \int_0^T (a - S_t)dt + \int_0^T \sigma_t S_t dW_t + \int_0^T Y_t S_t dN_t / \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \int_0^T (a - S_t)dt + \sum_{i=0}^T E[Y_i S_i \frac{dN_t}{dt}(i) / \mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand let's guess the density function of $\frac{dN_t}{dt}(i)$:

$$\begin{aligned} & P(\frac{dN_t}{dt}(i) < s) \\ &= P(N_{i+\epsilon} - N_i < s\epsilon) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor s\epsilon \rfloor} \exp(-\lambda\epsilon) \frac{(\lambda\epsilon)^k}{k!} \\ &= F(s) \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} f(s) &= F'(s) \\ &= \exp(-\lambda\epsilon)\epsilon \frac{(\epsilon s)^{\lfloor \epsilon s \rfloor - 1}}{\lfloor \epsilon s \rfloor!} - \exp(-\lambda\epsilon)(\lambda\epsilon)^{\lfloor \epsilon s \rfloor} \frac{(\lfloor \epsilon s \rfloor!)'}{(\lfloor \epsilon s \rfloor!)^2} \end{aligned}$$

Which means

$$E[S_T \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] = \beta_T + \int_{\mathcal{R}} E\left[\sum_{i=0}^T Y_i S_i\right] f(s) ds$$

$$\text{Where } \beta_T = \int_0^T (a - S_t) dt$$

Assumption: Suppose *à priori* that the option return is above the stock return, this is a formal hypothesis relaxed on the fact the Options are riskier than the Stocks, our vocation is to determine the probability $P(S_T \geq K)$ basing ourselves on the latter assumption, because afterward we would be in use of the so called **in-money** Options, this allows us to write the following

$$dC_t = (R_t + \epsilon) dt$$

Where $\epsilon > 0$

Which means

$$C_{t+1} = C_t + (R_t + \epsilon)$$

We could write out the option price as the following

$$C_t = A_t - K \exp(-r(T-t)) P(S_T \geq K)$$

Where $A_t = \exp(-r(T-t)) (\beta_T + \int_{\mathcal{R}} E[\sum_{i=0}^T Y_i S_i] f(s) ds)$

We can estimate the probability $P(S_T \geq K)$ by calculating the expectation $E[R_t / \mathcal{F}_t]$ Whereas

$$E[R_t / \mathcal{F}_t] = E[\ln(S_t) / \mathcal{F}_t] - E[\ln(S_{t-1}) / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

and

$$d \ln(S_t) = \frac{a - S_t}{S_t} dt + \sigma_t dW_t + \ln(Y_t + 1) - \frac{\sigma_t^2}{2} dt$$

Which means

$$\ln(S_t) - \ln(S_0) = \int_0^t \left(\frac{a - S_u}{S_u} - \frac{\sigma_u^2}{2} \right) du + \int_0^t \sigma_u dW_u + \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \ln(Y_i)$$

On the other hand

$$E[R_t/\mathcal{F}_t] = E[B_t + \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \ln(Y_i)/\mathcal{F}_t] - E[B_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{t-1}} \ln(Y_i)/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

Where $B_t = \int_0^t (\frac{a-S_u}{S_u} - \frac{\sigma_u^2}{2}) du$

4 The option multiplier and stock market

As a lot of scholars are in deep knowledge about the income effect, i have been inspired by the idea of the multiplier in economics to innovate a method between Options market and stock market, if we presume that the wealth out of selling a share in the stock market could be used for buying a frictional share of an option this could lead so far to stabilize the stock market, here is this equilibrium

$$S_i = \alpha_{i-1} C_i + S_{i-1} + \epsilon$$

Where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$

At time $i - 1$ the investor could decide out the frictional share of options that he would buy out of selling their share of stock market, the expectations of those investors could be grouped in a new space of probability that gather out their thoughts, their beliefs that the stock market using the method that i had innovated would be stabilized, such a kind of investors are aware about the values that above the risk premium that should benefit them the health of the stock market matters for them, under the universe H defined as the following

$$\frac{dH}{dQ} = \frac{\gamma S_t}{S_T}$$

Where Q is the risk neutral probability and $\gamma \geq 1$ the expectation of future Stock price would be defined as a function of the current stock price and we would look for the robustness of our method at getting the stock market kind of stable and we call it the Option multiplier where every time we suppose that the market is full of such investors there would be a sell of the stock and out of it the investor buys a share of options that adds to the stock current value. Arguably we could write

$$E[S_T/\mathcal{F}_t] = \gamma S_t$$

Afterward we could evaluate γ or the robustness of the Option multiplier to get the stock market stable

$$E^H[S_T/\mathcal{F}_t] = S_t + E^H\left[\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{T-i-1} C_{T-i}/\mathcal{F}_t\right]$$

Which means that $\gamma = 1$, our method then has the power to stabilize the stock market under this condition

$$E^H\left[\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{T-i-1} C_{T-i} / \mathcal{F}_t\right] = 0$$

This means that short selling of at least one option would happen during this process where every investor among this group would buy the stock at time t and sell it more conveniently making a profit or a loss at time $t + 1$, if there is a loss then shorselling the option is the right behavior that could offset this failure in the stock market, the above condition would follow through this process if we believe the existence of such traders in the market, our belief is based upon the rational explanation that the first aim of such a kind of investors is above all the market in a whole, by applying such a method they are sure that in the long term the market value of a given stock would not go downward, it would be the same at best as we had shown previously.

We should look for the right strategy (S_{i-1}, C_i) that avoids arbitrage, Let's start by emancipating that we start from a poor wealth, arguably zero and look for the strategy that doesn't allow wealth to be strictly positive at time T

$$\alpha_t C_{t+1} + S_t = 0$$

We have then

$$E[\alpha_{T-1} C_T + S_{T-1} / \mathcal{F}_t] = S_t + E\left[\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{T-i-1} C_{T-i} / \mathcal{F}_t\right]$$

We would have the following

$$\alpha_t C_{t+1} = E\left[\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{T-i-1} C_{T-i} / \mathcal{F}_t\right]$$

By expressing C_t as we had calculated it previously we obtain

$$\alpha_t (A_{t+1} - K \exp(-r(T - t - 1))) = E\left[\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (A_{T-i-1} - K \exp(-r(i + 1))) \alpha_{T-i-1} / \mathcal{F}_t\right]$$

This would define α as the following conditioning our vocation to build a strategy that avoids arbitrage at all costs, we would be euphoric enough to understand that any other strategy that starts from no wealth at time t can be used appropriately to be defined as an arbitrage strategy with another conditions, we look for the behavior of the Option

price, we need some restrictions in the Option price that fits with absence of arbitrage in our strategy, this leads to

$$A_{t+1} - K \exp(-r(n-1)) = A_t - K \exp(-rn)$$

$$E\left[\sum_{i=0}^{n-2} (A_{T-i-1} - K \exp(-r(i+1))) \alpha_{T-i-1} / \mathcal{F}_t\right] = 0$$

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